

BARRIERS TO INCLUSION: THE STRUGGLES OF WOMEN WITH DISABILITIES IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This study explores the employment challenges and discrimination encountered by women with disabilities and their implications for inclusion and empowerment. Employing a qualitative approach, the research utilizes in-depth interviews and focus group discussions to elucidate the multifaceted challenges surrounding the employment and unemployment of women with disabilities. The findings indicate that within a patriarchal and ableist social structure, disabled women confront profound economic hardship, exacerbated by discriminatory attitudes from colleagues and supervisors that further marginalize them. In addition to these challenges, their impairments also influence job performance and career trajectories, leading to a reduced social standing, lower self-perception, and diminished overall quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Women with disabilities experience multifaceted challenges in the peripheries of the global South. Developing countries are home to a substantial proportion of the world's disabled population. However, nations with limited resources often struggle to meet the needs of disabled individuals. In the developing world, disability and poverty are deeply intertwined, as poverty contributes to disability, and disability, in turn, reinforces poverty—an interdependent relationship acknowledged by recent scholarship (e.g., Grech, 2016). Women with disabilities face compounded gender-based disadvantages, further exacerbating their vulnerability. Poverty poses a dual burden for them,

disproportionately affecting their socio-economic status compared to non-disabled women and men. Consequently, women with disabilities often have little to no influence in economic decision-making. Exclusion from the labor market significantly impacts women with disabilities, jeopardizing their decision-making capacity, quality of life, and personal development. The challenges faced by women with disabilities in the global South received minimal scholarly attention, rendering their voices largely unheard. In the context of Pakistan, disabled women remain underrepresented in existing literature, with little to no research exploring the intersection of disability and gender. Moreover, the dynamics of this

intersection within Pakistan's broader socio-cultural framework, particularly in Pashtun society, remain largely unexamined. Research across diverse cultural contexts highlights how disability restricts access to employment opportunities, thereby compelling women with disabilities into dependency and disempowerment (e.g., Chindimba, n.d.). Likewise, gender-based roles and societal assumptions further marginalize women with disabilities, limiting their economic, social, and political participation and development (Arnade & Haefner, 2006). Consequently, the intersection of disability and gender carries significant implications for the empowerment and inclusion of women with disabilities

Women with disabilities constitute a heterogeneous group, with differences arising from the type and cause of disability, as well as individual characteristics such as age, socio-economic status, and cultural background. Recognizing and addressing this diversity is essential to effectively meeting their economic needs (National Women's Council of Ireland, 2008). Therefore, within welfare discourse and service provision, intersectional considerations are crucial for achieving meaningful outcomes through tailored support services. Addressing their needs within an intersectional framework can help mitigate the challenges they face in acquiring the necessary skills for labor market participation.

Women with disabilities face systemic exclusion from the job market due to multiple interrelated barriers, including limited access to education and skills development, pervasive negative attitudes, and an inaccessible built environment. As a result, they are more likely to experience economic inactivity and dependency (International Labor Office, 2006). In this regard, the economic contributions, dignity, and socio-economic conditions of women with disabilities have been consistently undervalued (Ngwena, 2007). Furthermore, in developing countries, a significant proportion of this population remains impoverished (DFID, 2008). This cycle of poverty is reinforced by structural barriers such as inaccessible infrastructure, limited educational opportunities, and restricted access to employment. Moreover, women with disabilities encounter formidable challenges in securing and retaining jobs due to both their impairments and the power

dynamics exerted by non-disabled individuals. In this context, Baldwin and Johnson (1998) argue that employment discrimination manifests in various ways, including outright refusal by employers and termination following absences due to illness or injury, further diminishing their chances of securing sustainable employment.

Disability remains an underexplored issue in Pakistan, particularly concerning the economic participation of women with disabilities. Research on disability and employability through a feminist lens has been sporadic, and existing literature largely fails to capture the lived experiences of women with disabilities in economic spheres. While gender plays a crucial role in empowerment and marginalization, its intersection with disability remains inadequately addressed. Therefore, this study holds significant importance in highlighting the economic challenges faced by women with disabilities and contributing to a more inclusive discourse.

Methodology

A qualitative research approach was employed to juxtapose and critically analyze the lived experiences of participants regarding the challenges they encounter in the job and labor market. The study recruited fifteen participants from nine Union Councils, District Swat, Pakistan. Data collection was conducted through a combination of focus group discussions and in-depth, face-to-face interviews, allowing for a comprehensive exploration of participants' perspectives. Data was collected from participants with mobility impairments ranging from mild to severe conditions. Snowball sampling was utilized to identify and recruit participants, ensuring access to individuals with disabilities. The following section presents the thematic analysis, results, and discussion of the study's key findings

Discrimination in the Workplace

Workplace discrimination significantly impacts the professional experiences, job performance, and employment retention of women with disabilities. In practice, gender inequalities embedded within societal structures intersect with the systemic disadvantages faced by disabled women, resulting in unique forms of exclusion and marginalization (National Women's Council of Ireland, 2008). These

compounded barriers not only limit access to employment opportunities but also create hostile work environments that undermine their professional growth and financial independence.

In this study, women participants shared their lived experiences, highlighting the multifaceted challenges they encounter in employment and the workplace. Their narratives serve as a collective voice against the patriarchal dominance and systemic hegemony exercised by both non-disabled men and women in professional settings. One participant, Nosheen, reflected on workplace inequality, recounting how her manager exploited her disability by paying her a significantly lower salary than her non-disabled colleagues. Her experience aligns with Gardiner's (1997) argument that disabled individuals face systemic discrimination solely based on their impairment. Furthermore, many disabled employees are unable to fully demonstrate their skills and professional capabilities due to a pervasive environment of fear and the constant threat of rejection, perpetuated by discriminatory attitudes of non-disabled coworkers and employers.

The structural exclusion of women with disabilities from the labor market is well-documented in existing literature. Fawcett (1996) similarly argues that disability status has a profound effect on labor market participation, reinforcing economic dependency and social marginalization. Employment and income, however, are crucial indicators of social inclusion and economic security for disabled women, enabling them to navigate and integrate into the demands of the modern world. In this context, Abberley (1999) asserts that achieving equal citizenship is contingent upon access to education and employment, emphasizing that proper education and vocational training play a pivotal role in skill development, which in turn enhances employment prospects.

Moreover, Nosheen's narrative corroborates with the findings of Dupper and Garbers (2004), who conclude that workplace discrimination against women with disabilities presents a fundamental challenge to their empowerment. Such systemic inequalities necessitate urgent policy interventions and institutional reforms to create inclusive work environments that foster equal opportunities and economic independence for women with disabilities.

Two participants in this study, both employed at a vocational center, encountered multiple challenges, including physical mobility barriers within the workplace and discriminatory treatment from both employers and colleagues. Their experiences highlight the systemic inequities that women with disabilities face in professional settings. One participant, Nosheen, recounted her personal struggle with workplace discrimination and unequal pay, stating:

[D]uring my job interview, I was offered a salary of 7,000 PKR per month, and I accepted. However, upon joining the center, my co-workers informed me that they were earning 12,000 PKR per month for the same work. If I were not in urgent need of supporting my family, I would have left. Although I earn money, I face numerous challenges. Mobility is a significant issue for me because of the steps inside the workplace. My employer constantly threatens me, saying that if I am unable to work, I should leave, despite the fact that I am already being paid significantly less than my colleagues.

Nosheen's experience depicts the multifarious barriers encountered by women with disabilities, including workplace inaccessibility, wage disparities, and employment instability and insecurity. Her situation also illustrates the convergence of economic exploitation and ableism. Ableist practices in the workplace produce professional marginalization, which affects Nosheen, her mental health, and her job performance. This empirical evidence emphasizes the need for policy measures that encourage inclusive workplaces and provide legal safeguards to protect individuals like Nosheen and other women with disabilities against employment discrimination.

Another participant shared her experience of workplace discrimination, stating that despite performing her job on par with her non-disabled colleagues, she was ultimately forced to resign. Both the manager and co-workers exhibited a lack of acceptance toward women with physical disabilities, driven by deeply entrenched negative stereotypes. As a result, these women were subjected to exclusion and mistreatment by their non-disabled colleagues, further reinforcing workplace marginalization. Such discriminatory practices have profound and far-reaching consequences for the dignity and self-worth of women with disabilities. Their fundamental rights

are systematically violated, compelling them to work in an oppressive and exclusionary environment that undermines their professional and personal well-being.

In this regard, Shumaila commented that:

I got a job at a female vocational center, and I was working very hard, but the management was not happy. This was my first experience working with non-disabled female employees. I felt very shy and nervous while working with them. Soon, I realized that their behavior was very negative, and it discouraged me. They told me that I was creating problems for the other female workers.

The case of Shumaila reflects the stereotypical attitudes toward the abilities of women with disabilities in the job and labor market. Consequently, such situations push them into a vicious cycle of poverty and other serious socio-economic challenges. The majority of the study's participants were unemployed, primarily due to a confluence of factors, including their impairment, patriarchy, discriminatory attitudes, inaccessible environment, and lack of skills. The Pashtun gender order encourages women's responsibilities in the private sphere while discouraging their involvement in public spheres.

Furthermore, co-workers and employers exhibited bias against female employees with disabilities. Participants in the study also experienced body shaming from non-disabled individuals, which negatively affected their performance and led to stress. For women with disabilities, body shaming serves as a form of categorization in which their so-called unacceptable and inferior characteristics are highlighted. Consequently, their exclusion from society is legitimized. Furthermore, this phenomenon does not reflect achievement, competence, or ability but rather reinforces their perceived inferior status in relation to their non-disabled counterparts (Boglieri & Shapiro, 2012), ultimately affecting their professional performance.

In this regard, terms such as "handicapped," "disabled," "epileptics," "blind," and "spastics" are often used to categorize individuals as a homogeneous group, which undermines their original identity. Additionally, some individuals are perceived as having a "spoiled identity," meaning that society not only attributes a negative characteristic to

them but also regards them as deviant (Goffman, 1963). As a result, these imposed characteristics become defining aspects of their social identity.

Negative labeling leads to a stigmatized identity, preventing women with disabilities from engaging in meaningful experiences. Furthermore, participants expressed that they felt a loss of identity due to the derogatory labels assigned to them by those around them. Many became victims of psychosocial distress due to being referred to by offensive terms such as "Gwada Khanzera" (amputee pig), "Shala" (leg amputee), and "Pa ta k yaw rag sewa de" (you have an extra wicked skill). This devaluation fosters psychological distress, further exacerbating their sense of exclusion, diminishing their self-efficacy, and impairing their overall performance.

Impairment and Physical Barrier

In addition to gender roles and patriarchal norms, the effects of impairment further complicate the employment opportunities of women with disabilities. During one of the focus group discussions, a participant, Zartaja, shared that although she did not face restrictions from her family, the physical effects of her impairment prevented her from securing a job. She experienced chronic pain while moving, which ultimately left her unemployed. "in this condition [paraplegic], when I try to cover a long distance, my leg starts to hurt, and then I cannot move further," Zartaja, said.

Zartaja's experience highlights how the physical consequences of impairment significantly impact her daily life, preventing her from seeking employment. This indicates that exclusion from the labor market is not solely a result of gender roles and patriarchy, but also of impairment-related barriers that hinder workforce participation.

Impairment exacerbates the intersectional challenges faced by women with disabilities, making their lived experiences uniquely complex. The interplay of impairment and poverty has profound implications for disabled individuals, posing challenges both at a personal level and within the broader societal structures of ableism and disablism. Intersectional barriers such as poverty, physical inaccessibility, restrictive gender roles, lack of skills and education, and unemployment are critical factors in understanding the lived realities of women with

disabilities in marginalized regions. Despite their distinct disability experiences, these issues have received little attention within disability research scholarship.

The built environment represents another significant obstacle to the employment of women with disabilities, further limiting their participation in the labor market compared to their male counterparts. Many participants in this study reported that inaccessible physical infrastructure hindered their ability to seek and maintain employment. Gul, one of the participants, shared her experience:

I am a wheelchair user, and I cannot get around on such uneven streets and buildings. I need a job to support my family. If I set out for anything from home, I face severe difficulties because the local transport, such as auto-rickshaw, does not have space for my wheelchair. It is difficult to go outside of the home.”

An accessible built environment requires awareness and resources at the state level. Unfortunately, in the majority of colonized countries, both of these essential prerequisites are lacking. Pakistan faces enormous economic crises and lacks the necessary resources to address the problem of inaccessibility. Additionally, there is little to no public awareness regarding the importance of accessibility and the inclusion of disabled people in various spheres of life. This means that a large number of disabled individuals remain excluded, violating their fundamental rights.

The effects of impairment in an inaccessible physical environment are significant concerns for disabled people in Pakistan. The government's lack of resources further exacerbates the challenges faced by women with disabilities. This issue is particularly critical in developing countries, including Pakistan, where a sizable population of disabled individuals experiences social exclusion with limited or no support from the government.

Challenges in Self-Employment

Women with disabilities have fewer opportunities to receive vocational training or participate in programs that could enhance their skills and improve their chances of employment. Consequently, they earn less than their non-disabled female and male counterparts. Moreover, self-employment depends

on skills, confidence, and motivation from peer groups and family members. However, women with disabilities often lack these prerequisites, making them financially dependent on their families. In Pashtun communities, women are discouraged from working in the public sphere. However, they can engage in home-based work including sewing, knitting, and embroidery. Although participants had the necessary skills, they lacked the required equipment to start or continue their work, which affected their ability to earn an income. As Sara stated:

I used a machine to sew clothes, and the women in our neighborhood would bring clothes for stitching. However, six months ago, my sewing machine broke down, and no one in my family is willing to take it for repairs. My income has stopped, and this is creating economic problems for me.

Living in an ableist society, women with disabilities struggle to meet even their most basic needs, including access to equipment essential for earning a dignified and independent livelihood. Access to proper tools is crucial for utilizing their skills and maintaining their dignity, particularly in a patriarchal society where gender roles strictly divide the private and public spheres. Rahila, in one of the focus group discussions, also shared a similar experience:

For females, outdoor business is not possible in Swat. Therefore, I managed to start my own small business. It is generating a reasonable income, but I do not have a quality sewing machine like professional tailors. It takes me two to three days to sew a single outfit.

Furthermore, several participants in this study highlighted the lack of training and skills as a factor that exacerbated their economic difficulties. They emphasized the importance of vocational skills for disabled women in generating income. These findings align with previous studies (e.g., Rioux, 1985), which demonstrate how limited training and poor education negatively affect the employability of women with disabilities, further increasing their vulnerability.

Physical barriers also limit their ability to acquire vocational skills. For wheelchair users, accessing vocational centers is particularly challenging. These training centers are not readily available in every

village or administrative unit in Pakistan. Only a few centers operate, and they serve large populations spread across remote areas. These challenges significantly impact the lives of women with disabilities, forcing them into passive and dependent roles within an able-bodied society.

Conclusion

Disabled people face multifaceted challenges in developing countries due to the intersection of poverty, gender roles, colonial legacies, and geopolitical factors. Women with disabilities are particularly marginalized at this intersection, rendering them unheard voices of the Global South. Their gender places them at heightened risk of exploitation, discrimination, economic hardship, dependency, and social exclusion. Furthermore, impairment effects and physical barriers exacerbate these challenges, leading to low social status, diminished self-esteem, and a lower standard of living. In addition, patriarchy and gender segregation within Pashtun society further limit the employability of women with disabilities. Exclusion from the labor market not only affects their economic independence but also impacts their personal well-being and societal participation. Those who manage to secure employment often face workplace discrimination and accessibility barriers. The empirical evidence from this study underscores the urgent need for measures to address unemployment among women with disabilities and to promote income-generating opportunities. Raising awareness within communities about the importance of employing women with disabilities and its positive societal impact is crucial. Expanding opportunities for meaningful employment will facilitate their social inclusion and empowerment, ultimately contributing to a more equitable and inclusive society.

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